

Rosa fläckar vid Kristianopels kyrka

Dokumentation av gästkollegeprojekt

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Rosa fläckar vid Kristianopels kyrka
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1. Inledning

I Kristianopels kyrka från ca 1620 återfinns i skymt utrymme (elskrubb under läktaren), ett större väggparti med - som det förefaller - kalkavfärgning i blekt rosa kulör. I långhuset finns även enstaka intensiva rosa fläckar i anslutning till golvlister etc. Frågeställningen är huruvida kyrkan verkligen i ett tidigare skede invändigt helt eller delvis varit avfärgad i rosa kulör samt om de mindre, intensivare ”fläckarna” är pigment eller rödalger?

2. Material och metoder

2.1. Prov och referenser

Four samples were removed from the church walls: three samples with pink coloring and one reference sample without pink coloring. Table 1 describes the samples. Further details about the samples, e.g. exact locations, sampling images and method can be found in Provtagningsprotokollet.

Sample name	Description	Image
Ref prov	No pink coloring present, sample from western wall. Mortar with white ground layer on surface.	
Prov 1	Sample from southern wall. Mortar with white ground layer and pink surface layer.	
Prov 2	Sample from western wall. Mortar with white ground layer and pink surface layer.	

Prov 3	Thin samples from western wall in vapenhuset. All samples show a pink surface on one side and white surface on the other side. The pink surface is shown in the image to the right.	
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2.2. Metod

Analytical methods: Samples were analyzed using optical microscopy with visible and ultraviolet light, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), x-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF, to look for elements that may indicate the presence of an inorganic pigment), and Fourier transfer infrared spectroscopy (FTIR, to look for indications of an organic pigment, paint binder, or biological material). For detailed information on instrument conditions and analysis locations, refer to the instrument reports for each analytical technique.

Sample preparation: All samples were analyzed as-received except for FTIR analysis of Prov 1, in which a small amount of the surface was scraped onto the ATR crystal using a scalpel. For detailed information on sample preparation and sampling locations, refer to the instrument reports for each analytical technique.

3. Resultat och diskussion

Optical microscopy

Microscopy with visible light did not show any clear indications that the pink coloring is either a paint or biological growth (e.g. algae). However, under ultraviolet light, it was clear that the mortar layer and the white ground layer do not fluoresce, while the pink layer does fluoresce (see Figure 1 for examples). Both organic pink pigments (e.g. rose madder) and biological growths can fluoresce when exposed to UV light. Thus, microscopy alone cannot exclude or identify the source of the pink coloring, but does give an indication that an organic layer is present in the pink layer.

Figure 1: Optical microscopy images of Ref prov (10x) at an interface between the mortar and ground under visible (a) and UV (b) light; Prov 1 (2.5 x) at an interface between the mortar and pink coloring under visible (c) and UV (d) light (note that brown circles in d are due to damage from UV light exposure at higher magnifications); Prov 2 (5 x and 10 x) in an area showing the white ground and pink coloring under visible (e, g) and UV light (f, h).

Scanning electron microscopy

SEM showed noticeable differences in microstructure of the areas of pink coloring compared to the white ground or mortar. In general, areas of pink color show chains of connected spheres, all of which are similar sizes (Figure 2 c, e, g, h). Areas of mortar or white ground show irregular particles creating a rough, porous surface or a smooth stone-like surface (Figure 2 a, b, d, f, i, j). Images in Figure 2 show two different points on the surface of Ref prov both with a layer of white mortar (a, b); two different points on Prov 1, one of which had pink coloring (c) and one which had bare mortar (d); two different points on Prov 2, one of which had pink coloring (e) and one which did not (f); two different points on the pink side of a piece from Prov 3 (g, h); and two different points on the white side of a piece from Prov 3 (i, j). More detailed information about the imaging locations is found in the SEM Instrument Report.

Figure 2: SEM images of Ref prov in two different spots (a, b); Prov 1 in a location with pink coloring (c) and without (d); Prov 2 in a location with pink coloring (e) and without (f); Prov 3 on the pink side (g, h); and Prov 3 on the white side (i, j).

Uniformly-sized, spherical chains would not likely be found in historical organic paint layers such as rose madder lake. Rather, the surface particles would appear more irregular in both size and shape. Examples of the microstructure of lake pigments can be seen in Figure 3 in an article by Szadkowski et al. 2022. Furthermore, biological growths in the form of bacteria on surfaces often grow in uniformly-sized spheres or ovals, suggesting that the pink layer is more likely composed of a biological growth than a pigment.

X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy

XRF analysis of the pink surfaces showed no evidence of elements related to inorganic pigments. Thus it is likely that the pink layer is composed of an organic material, which is in line with the results from optical microscopy. It may be possible that higher amounts of chlorine are present in the pink layers, which could suggest the presence of a biological material on the surface. Details about analysis locations can be found in the XRF Instrument Report. Figures 3 a and b show an overall view and closeup comparison of the mortar (black line) and white ground (red line), suggesting that both are primarily composed of calcium, iron and magnesium but with higher levels of iron and magnesium in the mortar itself.

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Figure 3: XRF spectra comparing the mortar, white ground and pink coloring of the samples: (a) Ref prov overall, (b) Ref prov closeup on smaller peaks, (c) Prov 1, (d) Prov 2 and (e) Prov 3.

Figure 3c compares the pink color (black line) to a spot of the white ground (red line). No peaks related to inorganic pigments are present in the pink layer, however, the chlorine peak is noticeable higher in the area of pink coloring. Figure 3d also compares pink coloring (red line) to the white ground (black line), but shows no noticeable differences in the chlorine peaks. There additionally seems to be a slightly higher chlorine peak in Figure 3e, which compares the pink side from a piece of Prov 3 (black line) to the white side of the same piece (red line). It unfortunately cannot be definitively stated that chlorine is present in higher amounts in the pink coloring, but may be possible.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

FTIR showed differences between areas with pink coloring and areas without pink coloring. Pink surfaces and white surfaces of pieces from Prov 3 were analyzed, as well as scrapings from the pink surface of Prov 1. Details about samples and sampling locations can be found in the FTIR Instrument Report.

Figure 4: FTIR spectra of (a) pieces from Prov 3, comparing both the pink and white sides; (b) pink surface material scraped from Prov 1 using a scalpel.

The white side from Prov 3 (Figure 4a) is assumed to be part of the white ground. This material shows peaks consistent with calcite (CaCO_3), including a peak for the C-O stretch at 1394 cm^{-1} , C-O out-of-plane bending at 871 cm^{-1} and C-O in-plane bending at 712 cm^{-1} (Derrick, et al. 1999). Small peaks at 1796 and 2514 cm^{-1} can also be attributed to CaCO_3 . This suggests that the white ground layer is composed of a lime-based paint, likely with no organic binder. Such peaks are also strongly visible in the scraped sample from Prov 1 (Figure 4b).

The pink sides from Prov 3 (Figure 4a) also show peaks from the white ground layer with the addition of peaks suggesting the presence of an organic material. The non-calcite peaks are consistent with peaks typically found in biological surface growths like algae or bacteria (Mayers et al. 2013, Gunawardena et al. 2013, Liang and Shen 2022). Biological surface growths like algae or bacteria are composed of proteins, lipids, phospholipids, carbohydrates and nucleic acids among other compounds. The presence of proteins can be attributed to the N-H stretch peak at 3280 cm^{-1} as well as the amide I band at 1631 cm^{-1} and amide II band at 1535 cm^{-1} . Lipids are attributed to asymmetric CH_3 stretch at 2960 cm^{-1} and the symmetric CH_2 stretch at 2933 cm^{-1} . A weak peak around 2850 cm^{-1} can also be attributed to the symmetric CH_3 and CH_2 stretches of lipids (Mayers et al. 2013, Derrick et al. 1999). The peak at 1243 cm^{-1} can be attributed to asymmetric stretch of P=O bonds, found in phospholipids and the phosphodiester of nucleic acids. Peaks at 1051 and 1025 can be attributed to the C-O-C stretches found in carbohydrates/polysaccharides (Mayers et al. 2013). Weak peaks potentially related to biological surface growths are also visible in the scraped sample from Prov 1 (Figure 4b).

The presence of a pink paint layer cannot be fully excluded, however such peaks are not easily identified in the presented spectra. Based on XRF analysis (see XRF Instrument report), there is no indication of an inorganic red pigment present, thus suggesting the presence of an organic pigment if a pigment is present at all. Pink organic pigments would most likely be lake pigments, in which a dye is bonded to a substrate, typically a metal salt like alum. Such pigments are often difficult to identify with FTIR due to the low dye concentrations in the pigment (Veiga et al. 2023). Because of this, we typically look for the presence of the substrate that the dye is bonded to. In FTIR, alum would show peaks at 3343 cm^{-1} for the OH stretch, 1644 cm^{-1} for the bending vibration of coordinated water, 1114 cm^{-1} for the Al-OH bend, and 983 cm^{-1} for the Al-O-Al stretch. The two strongest peaks would be found at 3343 and 1114 cm^{-1} (Veiga et al. 2023).

This pigment would typically also be combined with a binder that could be protein-, oil- or carbohydrate-based which could show peaks such as those described above for algae. However, a paint would often have a single main binder, while the spectra above show a mixture of lipids, proteins and carbohydrates. Furthermore, an oil binder would likely have a strong peak around 1750 cm^{-1} , which is missing in the spectra.

Due to the lack of strong peaks related to a lake pigment mordant, it seems more likely that the peaks in the FTIR spectra are related to a biological surface growth. However, the presence of a paint layer cannot be completely excluded as peaks for a paint could be overshadowed by stronger peaks from the biological growth and simply not visible using this analytical technique. Other analytical techniques, such as gas chromatography-mass spectrometry may be more suitable for clearly defining the presence of a possible pigment.

4. Slutsatser

Several samples from Kristianopels kyrka were analyzed to determine if a pink surface layer is a paint layer or a biological growth. The investigation at Riksantikvarieämbetets Kulturarvslaboratorium included optical microscopy with visible and ultraviolet light, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and x-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF). The presence of organic material in the pink surface layer was inferred by its tendency to fluoresce under ultraviolet light, the lack of peaks related to inorganic pigments in XRF spectra and the presence of peaks related to organic bonds in FTIR spectra. This information does not indicate if the pink layer is an organic paint or biological growth because both can exhibit such behavior. However, SEM images and closer interpretation of the FTIR peaks suggests that the pink layer could be a biological growth due to its uniformly-sized, spherical chains and the presence of peaks related to common growths like algae and bacteria. Additionally, the presence of peaks related to substrates for pink lake pigments was not identified in the FTIR spectra.

While the information presented in this study angles more towards the presence of a biological growth, a paint layer cannot be completely excluded using the instruments available at RAÄs Kulturarvslaboratorium. Other techniques which are not available in the laboratory, such as gas chromatography – mass spectrometry, may help to further identify the components of the pink layer.

5. Förvaring

Rådata från undersökningen lagras på Riksantikvarieämbetets rådatabas Lida (L:). Projektdokumentation lagras under diarienummer på G: och i Platina, samt fysiskt i Riksantikvarieämbetets arkiv.

Rådata, Provtagningsprotokoll och Instrumentrapporter laddades upp på dataförrådet Zenodo. DOI number 10.5281/zenodo.14754940.

Proverna från kyrkan förvaras fysiskt i Riksantikvarieämbetets Kulturarvslaboratorium.

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